

MEDICAL SCIENCES

INDICATION OF BACTERIAL - PHAGE SYMBIOSIS IN WASTEWATER AND ITS ROLE IN SUCCESSIONAL PROCESSES

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Abstract

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The article presents data on the indication of phage population in symbiosis with bacterial flora in wastewater of Govsany aeration station in Baku. In our research we identified a bacteriophage relative to *K. pneumoniae*, the indication of which complements the collection of phage population isolated from environmental objects. The material for the study was wastewater before and after mechanical cleaning. Selective and differential diagnostic environment were used for isolation and identification of microorganisms. Microorganisms of the Enterobacteriaceae family were identified by API-20 E tests (Biomerieux). Species composition of microorganisms detected from wastewater from Govsany aeration station: *E.coli*, *Streptococcus*, *Bacillus*, *S. aureus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Clostridium*, *Aspergillus ssp* and others. The study of lysogenic colonies allowed to note morphological differences in the isolated phages, which differ in size and turbidity. Moderate bacteriophages form turbid plaques, in which case the majority of bacterial cells remain lysogenic. Taking into account rather wide possibilities of phage population to change among the inhabitants of bacterial flora, as well as their resistance to survival in extreme conditions of existence, phages should be regarded as an active element in succession processes in nature.

Keywords: wastewater, bacterial-viral flora, phages, aeration station, external environment, lysis, *K.pneumoniae*, succession, symbiosis.

Klebsiella is one of the hospital infections, which makes them particularly dangerous. In the overwhelming majority of cases the cause (the causative agent of Klebsiellosis) remains unknown for a number of reasons: in one half of the cases the infection is caused by bacteria, and in the other half by viruses and intestinal infections become too common pathology. Human infectious pathology caused by bacterial - viral flora is a topical problem up to the present time. Different scientific schools in many countries of the world community have been engaged in the study of *K.pneumoniae* bacteriophages. The study of biochemical properties of bacteriophages allowed to widely use bacterial viruses to solve many problems in microbiology, virology, genetics, molecular biology and immunology. Due to the lack of statistical data on the detection of phage population in symbiosis with bacterial flora from wastewater, it became necessary to identify the presence of phages (bacteriophages) in wastewater, which can be regarded as extreme conditions for the growth and development of microorganisms in the epidemic spread of various infections of viral and bacterial

origin. In terms of our research on identification of phages in wastewater of Govsany aeration station in Baku with their possible participation in succession processes, the data on specificity of action of moderate phages, which penetrate into a bacterial cell, embed their DNA in the genome of the bacterium and in the form of a prophage transmit by inheritance from cell to cell without causing lysis of bacteria, are of interest.

On the basis of the above-mentioned **the aim of the work was:** indication and establishment of the spectrum of phage population of lysogenic bacteria and their symbiosis in wastewater of Govsany aeration station Baku.

The material for the study was wastewater before and after mechanical cleaning. Sowing bacterial flora in symbiosis with phage population we used a wide range of nutrient media of the world's leading companies 'BD' u 'Liofilchem', as well as 'Himedia' Microorganisms of Enterobacteriaceae family were identified by API-20E (Biomerieux) tests. The spectrum of microorganisms detected in wastewater during autumn-winter period of 2023 is given in Table 1.

Table 1:

Microorganisms	Govsany aeration drainage station					
	Before mechanical cleaning			After mechanical cleaning		
	10^{-4}	10^{-5}	10^{-6}	10^{-4}	10^{-5}	10^{-6}
E.coli	+	+	+	+	+	+
S.flexneri	+	+	+	+	+	-
E.faecalis	+	+	+	+	+	+
S.aureus	+	+	+	+	+	-
K.pneumonia	+	+	+	+	+	+
Enterobacter	+	+	+	+	-	-
Streptococcus	+	+	+	+	+	-
S.pneumonia	+	+	+	+	+	+
P.aeruginosa	+	+	+	+	+	-
Cl.perfringens	+	+	+	+	+	-
Bacillus spp	+	+	+	+	+	-
Aspergillus spp	+	+	+	+	+	-

Microbiological analysis of wastewater was carried out according to MU2.1.5.800-99, MUK4.2.1018-01. It was determined the number of coliform bacteria, shigella, salmonella, streptococci, pneumococci, clostridiums, bacilli and mould fungi of *Aspergillus* spp.. The common characteristic feature of wastewater after all types of treatment give the possibility of contamination by pathogenic or opportunistic microflora, as well as viruses, which is especially important nowadays.

The total microbial count was determined by the number of microorganisms contained in 1 ml of wastewater. For this purpose, from each sample and after the subsequent purification step, from different dilutions ($10^1, 10^6$), 1ml sample was sown into sterile Petri dishes, the sample was poured into melted and cooled to 45°C meat-peptone agar and the contents of the dishes were mixed evenly, avoiding the formation of bubbles. After solidification, they were placed in a thermostat and incubated at 37°C during 24 hours. Total and thermotolerant bacteria were determined by membrane filtration method. The measured volume of wastewater was passed through a membrane filter using vacuum filtration device PVF-35B, then the filter was transferred without inverting with sterile tweezers to Endo environment, ensuring complete adherence to the nutrient environment. The dishes were incubated in the thermostat at 37°C for 24 hours. For the isolation of *Streptococcus* genus representatives we used differential diagnostic media of blood and glucose agar.

Nutrient Broth was used for isolation of *K.pneumoniae* bacteriophage: 1 ml of daily culture of our museum bacterial strain was added to a tube with 5 ml of broth and incubated in the thermostat at 37°C for 24 hours. The bacterial mixture was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 15 min (Nüve, NF-800) and the supernatant was heated in a water bath (LOIP LB-140) at 45°C for 15 min. The supernatant was then passed through a 0.2 µm pore diameter filter and tested for the presence of phages by agar layer method. After 18-20 hours, the result was counted and the appearance of negative colonies on the bacterial lawn was analysed. As a result it was revealed that the *Klebsiella pneumoniae* showed lysogenic properties. A continuous culture lawn with and without lysis zones was observed on cups with Nutrient Aqar (Himedia). A piece of agar with lysed culture was cut with a sterile lancet from the cups with lysis zones with the examined *Klebsiella* culture and this material was used to pass phage in liquid environment with indicator culture. Then it was placed to thermostat and incubated for 18-20 hours at 37°C.

Results and discussion: The following spectrum of microorganisms was detected as a result of bacteriological studies of wastewater before and after mechanical cleaning: *E.coli*, *S.flexneri*, *E. faecallis*, *S.aureus*, *P.aeruginosa*, *S.pneumoniae*, *C.perfringens*, *K.pneumoniae*, *Bacillus* spp, *Aspergillus* spp and others. Of particular interest were *Klebsiella* microorganisms, which differed in biochemical properties before and after mechanical cleaning (Table 2).

Table 2

Biochemical properties of *K.pneumoniae* microorganisms isolated from wastewater before and after mechanical cleaning from Baku aeration station.

Substrate	<i>K.pneumoniae</i> -before mechanical cleaning	<i>K.pneumoniae</i> - after mechanical cleaning
Urease	+	+
Indole	-	-
Methyl red	-	+
Voges Proskauer	+	+
Citrate (Simmons)	+	+
Gelatin(22°C)	-	-
Lysine decarboxylase	+	+
Malonate	+	+
Mucate	+	+
Sodium alginate	+	-
Gas from glucose	+	+
Lactose	+	+
Dulcitol	-	+
Organic acid media:		
Citrate	-	+
D-Tartrate	+	-

K.pneumoniae are biochemically active and are able to break down lactose, but do not produce hydrogen sulphide. They are able to utilise citrate, malonate, break down urea and unlike other species, such as *K.oxytoca*, do not produce indole. Differentiation within the genus into subspecies of *K.pneumoniae* is made on the basis of biochemical properties. As can be seen from

the table before and after mechanical cleaning the biochemical tests are different from each other.

Some of them are aerobes, the others facultative anaerobes, the cells are bacilliform, but the sizes also vary from 0,3 to 1,5 µm and from 0,5 to 5,0 µm.

Pic. 1 -Biochemical properties of *K.pneumoniae* before and after mechanical cleaning:

There were determined lysates (4+plus) to *K.pneumoniae* bacteria relative to phage population activity. The presence of Klebsiella culture lysis zones or negative growth colonies of microorganisms indicated the presence of bacteriophages in wastewater before and after mechanical cleaning from Govsany aeration station. The size and shape of negative colonies is one of the characteristics of phage. Before mechanical cleaning, the bacteriophage formed cloudy mucous small negative colonies (0.5-1.0 mm), and after mechanical cleaning, relatively transparent mucous and different in structure rounded colonies of 1.5-2.5 mm in size. Lytic activity was up to 10^9 degrees according to Appelman's method.

Conclusions:

1. As a result of our study it was found that currently used methods in the practice of phage indication do not give a hundred per cent efficiency and none of them is universal.

2. Phages have a great reproductive capacity, due to which within a short time after infection of the cell, it releases individual viral particles. Thousands of viral particles can form in a single bacterial cell, such fecundity is accompanied by lysis.

3. The isolation of bacteriophages from wastewater allowed us to identify 2 isolates of phages active against *Klebsiella pneumoniae* bacteria.

4. The study of lysogenic colonies allowed us to note morphological and biochemical differences in the

isolated phages, which differ in size and turbidity. Turbid plaques form moderate bacteriophages, because most of the bacterial cells inside the plaque remain lysogenic.

5. The bacteriophage K.pneumoniae detected in the wastewater of Govsany aeration station in Baku added the collection of phage population isolated from environmental objects with its use in epidemiological marking of the epidemic process

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